

A Large Scale Characterization of the Dielectric Properties of Heterogeneous Layered Rock Salt

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Abstract—Although there are several methods described in the literature to accurately measure the complex permittivity of solid dielectrics at radio frequencies in a laboratory environment, none of these methods allow for a large-scale accurate characterization of natural ionic dielectrics. The work presented here reports results of the dielectric permittivity retrieved from *in situ* measurements in a Romanian salt mine. Measurements were performed in the 164–174-MHz bandwidth, over a propagation distance of 100 m. The characteristics of the layers of sedimentary salt are determined from measurements using a least mean square fitting algorithm, based on a detailed propagation model for a heterogeneous medium. The coupling of the instrumentation is also considered. The proposed approach demonstrates great promise for a large number of applications.

Index Terms—Complex permittivity ionic crystals, radio wave propagation, salt mine.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE are several methods available to accurately measure in a laboratory environment the complex permittivity of discrete samples of solid dielectric media: some use time domain analysis [1], [2], other a shorted rectangular waveguide [3], [4], the method of cavity perturbation [5], [6], or the capacitance method [7]. There are also specific methods for low-permittivity and low-loss homogeneous materials [8], [9], for liquid dielectrics [10], [11] etc. There are other methods like spatial time domain reflectometry that allow for *in situ* soil moisture profile determination [12] or even the porosity distributions of water saturated granular media [13]. However, none of these approaches permits a large-scale characterization of natural ionic dielectrics, which represents the goal of this article.

A large-scale characterization also serves as the first step toward the construction of a cosmic neutrino radio detector in a salt mine. It is worth mentioning that all cosmic neutrino detectors require usage of large natural detector media (such as atmosphere, sea water, ice, and salt ore) as target material [14]–[16], material that has to be characterized prior to construction. This is impetuous because the most sensible problem connected to a cosmic neutrino radio detector in a natural salt is the capability to reconstruct the features of the

cosmic particles that interact in the salt from the interaction products, i.e., radio waves produced by Askaryan effect [17]. The radio waves that appear at the interaction point travel through salt, so the medium itself has a huge impact on results and their interpretation. In this article, the properties of *Unirea* salt mine were investigated as a possible location for the construction of a radio neutrino detector, with the help of man-made, controllable radio waves.

Hapke [18] already remarked that the regime of radio wave propagation in nonideal media is not well understood. He also suggested that an effective-medium theory can be considered to calculate the permittivity that describes the medium, permittivity that is directly connected to the attenuation of radio waves in the dielectrics (this aspect will be further detailed in Section II).

The same issue—good geophysical description for radio wave propagation—has been addressed by other types of applications: locating buried utilities [19]–[21], profiling the subsurface of highway pavement, etc. Moreover, other authors [22], [23] pointed out the difficulty to model or predict the propagation of communication radio waves in non-conventional media, such as the ones after disaster situations. Although theoretical approaches have been reported in [24] and [25] and others, models for propagation are rare because the heterogeneity in the medium clearly affects radio waves.

Section II of this article presents an elaborate radio propagation model for N layered media that includes instrumentation effects (i.e., antenna behavior when boreholed in dielectric and coupling effects). The model directly links the properties of the medium to the measurable quantities. The rest of the section describes the measurements and instrumentation used. Section III outlines the results obtained and the implications on both purity of salt reservoir and the construction of a cosmic neutrino detector. Section IV summarizes the main conclusion. The work includes the Appendix with information on salt diapir characteristics from radio wave propagation perspective.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELING AND MEASUREMENTS

A method to determine the permittivity of a dielectric medium at radio frequencies from *in situ* measurements is presented in [26]. A very similar procedure was applied in [27] to determine the radio attenuation length for the Cote Blanche salt mine, in the 125–900-MHz bandwidth, over distances of up to 169 m.

The measurement principle relies on the fact that the intensity of the electric field is attenuated in the medium where the

Manuscript received May 31, 2019; revised August 16, 2019 and October 1, 2019; accepted December 6, 2019. This work was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) through the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant 714637.

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Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TGRS.2019.2958849

Fig. 1. Measurement principle: several cylindrical holes are drilled in a wall of the salt mine. The distances between the holes are $r_1 = 10$, $r_2 = 50$, and $r_3 = 100$ m. The emission antenna (Tx) is inserted into the first borehole—marked by (1) in the figure. The reception antenna (Rx) is moved in between the holes (2)–(4). The Tx and Rx antennas are connected to a vector network analyzer (VNA). The figure is not to scale. In the background, a portion of one wall in *Unirea* salt mine is visible.

radio waves propagate, thus measurements of the electric field (or voltage) after a certain distance from a known emitting source allow for the determination of the attenuation length (i.e., the distance where the electric field intensity drops at $1/e$ of its initial value, e being Euler’s number), which is a measure of the dielectric permittivity of the medium. For a nonideal dielectric medium at least two measurements at two different propagation distances are required to characterize its complex permittivity, which can be expressed in terms of its frequency-dependent real and imaginary parts

$$\epsilon_r = \Re\{\epsilon_r\} - j\Im\{\epsilon_r\}. \quad (1)$$

The radio waves are produced and intercepted with the help of antennas, thus radio antennas will represent the main working instrument. To minimize the propagation effects the antennas should be inserted in air-filled boreholes drilled in the medium to be characterized. Due to spacing limitations vertical dipole antennas are preferred. The spacing also limits the minimum measurement frequency, as the physical dimension of the antenna is inversely proportional to the resonance frequency. In this article, the measurements were performed in the 164–174-MHz frequency band.

A schematic of the measurement principle is presented in Fig. 1. The emitting antenna (Tx) is positioned in borehole 1 and the receiving antenna (Rx) in borehole 2 (at 10 m from borehole 1), 3 or 4 (at 50 and 100 m, respectively). Boreholes are perpendicular to the interface salt wall–air. The background of Fig. 1 represents the wall where the holes were drilled. The Rx antenna is always followed by an amplifier (not shown in the picture).

The measurements can be performed with a vector network analyzer (VNA). The VNA is a widely used instrument for radio frequency design applications that measure both amplitude and phase properties. The basic architecture of a network analyzer involves a signal generator, a test set, one or more receivers and a display. The receiver is responsible for the measurements.

Most VNAs have at least two test ports (i.e., emitting and receiving), allowing measurements of both S_{11} —the reflection

coefficient of the network (i.e., what is emitted and reflected backward to the transmitter)—and S_{21} , i.e., the forward transmission through the network (i.e., what is actually recorded by the receiver). The transmission coefficient S_{21} between the Tx and Rx antennas (separated by a distance r_k) can be expressed in terms of phase ϕ_k and amplitude A_k

$$S_{21,k} = A_k \exp(j\phi_k). \quad (2)$$

This method has the advantage that S_{21} can be directly measured using a VNA without the need of synchronization between emission and reception or further calibration.

By dividing the two measured electrical field intensities/voltages [i.e., $k = 1, 2$ in (2)] at two random distances from the transmitting antenna (e.g., r_1 and r_2), the average permittivity along the propagation line can be obtained. This is valid because at both measurements the receiving chains (i.e., antennas, cables, and amplifier) remain identical. In addition, by taking the ratio of measurements the effects of the amplifier and short cables cancel out.

From (1) and (2), the complex permittivity can be retrieved [26]

$$\Re\{\epsilon_r\} = \frac{(\phi_2 - \phi_1)^2 - [\ln(r_2 A_2 / r_1 A_1)]^2}{\omega^2 \epsilon_0 \mu_0 (r_2 - r_1)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\Im\{\epsilon_r\} = \frac{2(\phi_2 - \phi_1)[\ln(r_2 A_2 / r_1 A_1)]}{\omega^2 \mu_0 (r_2 - r_1)^2} \frac{1}{\omega \epsilon_0} \quad (4)$$

where μ_0 (ϵ_0) is the permeability (permittivity) of vacuum, and ω is the angular frequency equal to $\omega = 2\pi f$ (f is the frequency).

A problem with this method is that formulas (3) and (4) can be applied in this form only if measurements of $A_{2/1}$ and $\phi_{2,1}$ are within distances smaller than a wavelength. If this is not the case, the phase recorded by the measuring instrument also includes the “propagation phase” (i.e., $2\pi r_k / \lambda$, with λ being the wavelength in the medium that is permittivity-dependent).

With this in mind, the solution for the real and imaginary parts of the permittivity can be determined by applying the least mean square (LMS) methods to measurements, starting from (3) and (4). For measurements at a frequency of ~ 170 -MHz results indicated the corresponding value of the permittivity $\epsilon_r = 5.7737 - j0.1185$ (a detailed description of the measurements is presented in Section II-B).

Other theoretical studies [28] shown the real part of the permittivity to have values smaller by at least 2%, a variation too large to be accepted in some applications. In addition, the same method presented also applied to higher frequencies (i.e., ~ 400 MHz), resulting in a value of the real part of the permittivity of 1.324, which is close to the permittivity of vacuum. It is clear that this simple method too has some flaws and the medium should be more accurately described. This is accomplished in Section II-A that models the propagation of radio waves in the salt mine considering the most important properties of the salt mine in the context of radio wave propagation. The characteristics of the salt reservoir (i.e., a diapir), together with the internal heterogeneous structures, rock porosity, and water effects, etc. are detailed in the Appendix.

A. Radio Wave Propagation Model for a Heterogeneous Layered Medium

Some general effects connected to the propagation of radio waves were studied in the previous work [29]: electromagnetic induction (EMI) of the Earth and the induced polarization (IP) effect related to the relaxation of polarized charges in the formation of rocks. Both phenomena occur in rock formations in areas of mineralization (i.e., areas with mineralized particles) and hydrocarbon reservoirs [30] situated in the peripheral areas of the dome (which is not the case for *Unirea* salt mine, investigated in this article). Moreover, these effects are significant at kilo Hertz frequencies, and thus propagation of radio waves at 200 MHz will not be affected.

The model described by (3) and (4) assumes a homogeneous medium between the receiving and emitting antennas. In reality, a salt diapir is formed by the layers of sedimentary salt emerged from the evaporation of ancient seas [31]. In the work presented here, the layers are almost parallel to the antennas used for measurements. This hypothesis could be verified at the site of the experiment because the layers in the salt wall were visible with the naked eye.

Propagation of radio waves in a heterogeneous medium is affected by several phenomena: reflections at the separation interfaces, absorption, and scattering on naturally occurring impurities within each layer. Among the three, the main energy loss is due to reflections [32]. Diapirs produce salt with a negligible brine content and minimal impurities, and thus birefringence is unlikely to occur [33].

As mentioned, radio waves can be produced by antennas. A finite length dipole in free space produces a primarily spherical wavefield radiated from the feed point that propagates radially. The shape of the field is roughly spherical, superimposed on the reflected field at the end of antenna (also roughly spherical). As a result, the primary wavefront exits the antenna mainly in the radial direction [34]. Referring to Fig. 1, the situation when the dipole is positioned in a borehole is very similar, as simulated in [35].

The waves emitted by the Tx antenna propagate first in the air of the borehole, thus a first reflection will occur at the interface between air and the first layer of salt. The reflection coefficient at this first interface is R_1 and depends on the complex permittivity of the first layer of salt ϵ_1 . Afterward each layer of the salt of permittivity ϵ_i will produce a new reflection, R_i , $i > 2$. Generally, the reflection depends on the permittivities and the incidence angle of the wave. Plane wave reflection coefficients can be used for spherical waves with small errors. The spherical nature begins to dominate at gazing angles [34].

The attenuation in each layer $F_{(i-1)i}$ (between each two interfaces $i - 1$ and i) is equal to

$$F_{(i-1)i} = F_{0i} \exp(-\alpha z_{i-1}) \exp(-j\beta z_{i-1}) \quad (5)$$

where F_{0i} is the field intensity at the input of layer $i - 1$, the thickness of the layer is z_{i-1} , and

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{\Re\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}}{2} \left[\left(1 + \left(\frac{\Im\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}}{\Re\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}} \right)^2 \right)^{1/2} - 1 \right]} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. Flow graph describing the measurement principal and propagation model. The directions of the arrows show the wave propagation direction. The whole system can be regarded as an overall 2-port (suggested by the dashed contour line): port (1) representing the transmission port and port (2)-the reception port, both with a characteristic impedance of 50 Ω . Ports (1) and (2) represent also the connection ports to the output and input of the measuring device, the VNA.

and

$$\beta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{\Re\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}}{2} \left[\left(1 + \left(\frac{\Im\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}}{\Re\{\epsilon_{i-1}\}} \right)^2 \right)^{1/2} + 1 \right]} \quad (7)$$

represent the attenuation and phase constant in layer $i - 1$, whose permittivity is ϵ_{i-1} . The attenuation length L is inversely proportional to the attenuation constant, $L = 1/\alpha$.

A compact characterization of a N -layer model has been introduced in the literature more than 50 years ago (see [36], [37]) without including the effects of the instrumentation (i.e., antennas). Other results obtained using the reflection coefficient measured with a single antenna are presented in [38], but the model can be applied to a few layers, with a thickness of a few centimeters. Also the computational complexity is very high.

The work addressed here includes in the analysis the effects of the antennas in terms of: antenna coupling with the environment, and the different behavior of antennas when working in a dielectric medium other than air. The latter has been the subject of extensive simulations [35], [39], and it was resolved in [40] using a semiempirical model. It should be mentioned at this point that the only effect that could not be modeled is the effect of scattering on impurities within each layer. Even though the overall effect in terms of amplitudes is small, each scattering will produce a phase shift. This systematic error was estimated in [40]. All effects associated with antennas, together with the propagation model can be characterized by a flow graph. A flow graph is a set of nodes interconnected by branches, which together represent a set of linear equations. The flow graph is associated with a number of simple rules (generally known as Mason's rules [41]) which enable every possible solution to be obtained.

The flow graph describing the measurements with all associated effects is presented in Fig. 2. The functionality of antennas in salt is described by the scattering coefficients: $S_{11,as}$ —the input reflection coefficient, $S_{22,as}$ —the reflection coefficient resulted from coupling with the environment, and $S_{21,as}$ —the forward transmission. Each layer is characterized by a factor F_{ij} and the interfaces between layers by R_i . The

terms R_1 and R_{n+1} mark the air–salt and salt–air interface, respectively, as the boreholes where antennas are positioned are filled with air. The directions of the arrows show the wave propagation direction. The closed loops formed by single/multiple cells in the graph suggest the multiple reflections within the same layer/layers.

The overall two-port system can be characterized by the scattering matrix $[S]$, the coefficient S_{11} being the input reflection coefficient of the network and S_{21} the forward transmission through the network. By applying Mason’s rules, after some algebraic equations and rearrangements, the scattering parameters S_{11} and S_{21} have the form [40]

$$S_{11} = S_{11,as} - \frac{S_{12,as}S_{21,as}}{S_{22,as}} + K \quad (8)$$

$$S_{21} = \frac{(S_{12,as}S_{21,as}) \cdot F_{12} \cdot F_{23} \cdot \dots \cdot F_{nn+1} A_{n+1}}{\Delta} \quad (9)$$

where

$$K = 2S_{12,as}S_{21,as}R_1 \left(1 + \frac{S_{22,as} \cdot R_1 - 1}{\Delta} \right) + \frac{S_{12,as}S_{21,as}}{S_{22,as} \cdot \Delta}. \quad (10)$$

In (9), the index $n + 1$ represents the last interface (salt–air) and A_{n+1} represents the transmission coefficient in the air of the borehole of the receiving antenna (assumed to be equal to 1 since the transversal dimension of the hole is 7.5 cm). The quantity Δ is

$$\Delta = 1 - S_{22,as} \cdot P \quad (11)$$

with

$$P = [R_1 + R_2 F_{12}^2 + R_3 F_{12}^2 F_{23}^2 + R_4 F_{12}^2 F_{23}^2 F_{34}^2 + \dots]. \quad (12)$$

The terms S_{11} and S_{21} can be directly measured with a VNA, the measurement technique and instrumentation being described in Section II-B.

B. Measurements and Instrumentation

The measurements in this article were performed in *Unirea* salt mine in Slanic Prahova (Romania), one of the largest salt mine complexes in Europe, with a total surface of 80 000 m², whose exploitation started in 1943 [42]. The main chamber is located at a depth of ~ 200 -m, providing a stable measurement environment. The climate allows for a very long-term conservation due to the constant temperature inside the mine (13 °C), the atmospheric pressure higher with 18 mmHg than the surface air pressure, and dry air conditions, disregarding the season [42]. A more elaborate discussion regarding the characteristics of the mine and formation conditions is presented in the Appendix.

All measurements were performed using a NA7300A VNA (Deviser). The instrument recorded the S -scattering parameters between its input and output 50- Ω ports. A pair of vertical polarization, omni-directional dipoles used for measurements in the 164–174-MHz bandwidth (produced by Kathrein, model K552628) was connected to the ports of the VNA using 50 Ω N-type coaxial cables (EC400 +). All aspects regarding antenna positioning, coupling, and behavior when boreholed in salt, power loss in air, etc. are discussed and characterized as given in [40].

Fig. 3. Measurement instrumentation used. On the floor of the room the Tx and Rx antennas are presented; the connections (i.e., cables) to the VNA ports can be observed. The details on the left and right sides illustrate the antennas inserted into the holes drilled in the wall of the mine chamber. The distance r_k on the wall between each two holes varies from 10 to 100 m.

Other RG 58 coaxial cables (both having a length of 1-m) were used to interconnect the SMA input–output of an amplifier (Aaronia, model UBBV1) with the Rx antenna. The effects of the RG 58 cables were excluded in the data postprocessing. The amplifier has an almost constant gain of about 40 dB in the 50 MHz–1-GHz band and a 3.5-dB noise figure. The system had a constant transmission power of 10 dBm.

To perform the measurements the dipole antennas were intruded in salt because these cylindrical boreholes were made in a wall of salt mine (see Fig. 3). The mine chamber walls are thicker than 100 m, and the total depth of the salt diapir is more than 500 m, which makes the walls of the mine chamber to be positioned below and above at least 100 m of salt. The boreholes are parallel to each other, at the same height from the chamber floor, each hole having a total depth of 1.2 m, and a diameter of 75 mm. The distance between the holes was accurately measured with a laser tape.

Generally, salt mines are expected to be radio quiet places since the soil above absorbs most of the radiation, natural or man-made. This is particularly necessary in the case of a cosmic detector because the requirements to be fulfilled such as a cosmic event to be considered triggered and reconstructed should be determined in such a way that the detection efficiency is the highest. This is necessary because one of the main problems associated with radio detectors is signal recognition under noise. For this the radio background was carefully measured and a mean value of -97 dB was found in the 164–174-MHz band. This highly surpasses the value of the thermal noise in the specified bandwidth of the receiver, evaluated at approx. -130 dB. The value was determined from the 3.5-dB noise figure of the amplifier—as specified in the datasheet provided by the manufacturer—and an ambient temperature of 286 K that would represent a maximal limit for the noise temperature of the antenna.

Measurements were repeated in three campaigns in: July 2017, November 2017, and February 2018. Variations in results between campaigns are below 1%, and this would be the limit of the statistic uncertainty, considering that the salt mine is a very stable environment in terms of temperature, composition, and internal structure of the salt diapir. A full

discussion about statistical and systematic errors is presented in Section III-C.

To eliminate the systematic errors introduced by the measurement setup, a null calibration of the whole measuring system (network analyzer and cables) was performed. This also excludes reflection losses and changes in the measurement reference planes caused by the connection of most cables.

To increase the accuracy of the measurements, the VNA measured the frequency-dependent complex ratio $S_{11}(f)$ and $S_{21}(f)$ at 1601 evenly stepped operating frequencies in the nominal frequency band. The sweep time was set to 2 s, and an averaging factor of 10 was chosen to improve the signal-to-noise ratio.

III. RESULTS

A. Characterization of Sedimentary Salt

The model presented in Section II-A and described by (8)–(12) includes: the behavior of antennas in salt (the terms marked by indexes a, s), coupling of the instrumentation with the environment [e.g., the product in (11)], reflections and multiple reflections within each layer, attenuations, etc. Some discussions are necessary to decrease the complexity of the calculus.

The first simplifying hypothesis that will be adopted is with regard to the reflection terms. As described in Section II-A, the term R_i depends on the permittivity of two consecutive layers $i - 1$ and i and also on the incidence angle of the radio waves. The narrow spatial radiation pattern of the antenna in salt [39], together with Snell's refraction law [41], predicts incidence angles very close to the normal incidence after the first interface of separation. At the first interface (air–salt) larger incidence angles may result in energy lost through the borehole (the antenna is situated close to the border of separation between the salt wall and free space). However, the power lost through the borehole has been measured, and it was found to be 50 smaller than the power emitted in salt, thus negligible [40]. Moreover, the theoretical work on low-loss media predicted that the reflection coefficient between two consecutive layers may be simplified to [43]

$$R_i = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_{i-1}} - \sqrt{\epsilon_i}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{i-1}} + \sqrt{\epsilon_i}} \quad (13)$$

thus the dependence on the incidence angle can be disregarded.

The second simplifying hypothesis concerns the term P in (12). It was calculated analytically that products that contain terms of higher orders (i.e., $F_{i-1,i}, i > 4$) will introduce overall variations smaller than 10^{-4} in the expression. This limit is lower than the resolution of the VNA, which means that the presence of this term in the model is expendable. This leads to an approximation

$$P \approx [R_1 + R_2 F_{12}^2 + R_3 F_{12}^2 F_{23}^2 + R_4 F_{12}^2 F_{23}^2 F_{34}^2] \quad (14)$$

which implies that the measured coefficient S_{11} can be used to provide details relevant to the first five layers of salt only.

Another aspect regarding attenuation is that the term $F_{i-1,i}$ depend not only on the permittivities but also on the thickness of the layers according to (5). Fortunately, each reflection at

the separation border will produce a phase shift [18] that can be retrieved from the measured S_{21} . This will further allow for the determination of the total number of layers n and their thicknesses z_i .

All calculus were performed considering a high purity of the rock salt in *Unirea* salt mine [31], expected from the geological formation process of a diapir. This assumption is supported by results reported in the literature, that show a total concentration of impurities of 22.7851 g/kg in salt samples collected from *Unirea* mine [44]. The high purity assumption requires that the real part of the permittivity does not vary from layer to layer [45].

For a pure NaCl symmetrical lattice, the dielectric permittivity is an isotropic measure [46]. In addition, a reasonable impurity concentration will only affect the imaginary part of the permittivity, as detailed in Section III-B.

The previous work of the author determined the permittivity of the first layer of salt to be $\epsilon_1 = 5.625 - j0.0708$ in the frequency range of interest [40]. Laboratory work performed by Meng and his collaborators [28] found that $\Re\{\epsilon_r\} = 5.63 \pm 0.05$ at frequencies between 2.2 and 18 GHz, and this result was adopted here (it is expected that this value does not vary at millimeter and longer wavelength [28]). Moreover, there are no theoretical models on how a low concentration of impurities in the NaCl ionic crystal lattice could modify the real part of the permittivity.

The measured quantities S_{11} and S_{21} [corresponding to (8) and (9)] contain information about all constituent layers in between the emission and reception antennas. Theoretically speaking, a Levenberg–Marquardt fitting algorithm could match the complex permittivity of each layer together with its thickness. In practice, such an algorithm does not converge due to the large number of unknowns. Moreover, such an algorithm leads to false solutions unless a convenient starting guess is available.

The numerical code used in this article to characterize the layers of sediments (in terms of permittivity and thickness of each layer) was written as a fitting algorithm that minimizes simultaneously in the LMS sense the real and imaginary parts of term P , extracted from (8) and combined with measurements of S_{11} . This was possible because all the terms $S_{ij,as}$ (that refer to properties of antennas radiating in salt) have been already calculated elsewhere [40]. Also, the fitting algorithm in an internal loop uses the total number of layers n and their thickness z_i based on phase shifts retrieval.

The LMS fitting algorithm for term P also provides details not only on the thickness of the first four layers of salt but also on their permittivities. The thicknesses are: $z_1 = 0.1029$, $z_2 = 0.1582$, $z_3 = 0.1715$, and $z_4 = 0.0376$ m. The algorithm also determines the permittivities for the first five layers because reflection coefficients are calculated between two consecutive layers (thus an extra layer is needed). The imaginary parts of the permittivities were found to be at 170 MHz: $\Im\{\epsilon_1\} = 0.0708$, $\Im\{\epsilon_2\} = 0.0107$, $\Im\{\epsilon_3\} = 0.0587$, $\Im\{\epsilon_4\} = 0.0603$, and $\Im\{\epsilon_5\} = 0.08$. Variations within the bandwidth is shown in Fig. 4, calculated for a discrete number of frequencies.

Results obtained have shown that the first 10 m of salt where the radio waves propagate are formed by 76 layers of salt,

Fig. 4. Imaginary part of the permittivity for the first five layers. The line marked by “+” corresponds to the first layer; the line marked by “*”, the second layer; the line marked by “o”, the third layer; the line marked by triangles, the fourth layer; and the continuous line, the fifth layer.

with thicknesses varying from 0.0045 to 0.278 m. The number of layers increases to 153 for 50 m of propagation, and to 296 after 100 m (layers with a thickness of almost 1 m are also present). The results of the fitting algorithm of (9) are limited by the sensitivity of the used VNA in the sense that measurements performed with higher precision instrumentation would lead to a larger number of fully determined layers [more terms would be relevant in (9)]. Note that the other methods, such as 2-D electrical resistivity tomography, allow media characterization with a resolution of 0.25–0.5 m and are also limited to highly irregular or complex geological features [47]. Others, such as cross-hole GPR, generally necessitate that the boreholes where the emitter and receivers are inserted to be separated by 10 m at most [48]. In addition, they require that the number of measurements to be very high, obtained with either a large number of receivers [49], or very long boreholes where the antennas are moved along [50].

B. Purity of the Salt Diapir

A theoretical model to determine impurities in each layer was considered, since it is expected that each layer of salt to have a permittivity given by its constituents [51]. Generally, the complex frequency-dependent dielectric permittivity of a natural deposit is determined by its structural properties and its thermodynamic state [28].

In the specific case of alkali halides the imaginary part of the permittivity reflects three contributions: ionic conduction, dielectric relaxation, and multiphonon quasiresonant processes [28]. The latter characterizes the photon–phonon interactions. In ionic crystals such as NaCl they have a significant contribution in the millimeter wave and far infrared. The dielectric relaxation magnitude is several orders of magnitude larger than the ionic conduction (except at high temperatures).

The main impurities detected in the NaCl in *Unirea* salt mine are Al, Ca, Ti, Fe, K, Cr, V, Mn, Ni, Zn, Cu, Pb, Sr, and Ba [44]. For NaCl crystals the presence of an external electrical field generates ion mitigation which is the most

important mechanism of electrical conduction. The contribution to the ionic current due to the motion of anion vacancies was neglected as it is a few orders of magnitude smaller [28].

As a consequence, all impurities were treated as divalent cations, following the approach of [28]. This is supported by the other work [52] that states that in alkali halides the isolated positive vacancies (created thermally Schottky defects, or as charge compensators to maintain the crystal electrical neutrality) are mainly responsible for the current transport.

Using the mathematical model reported in [28] and applying an inverse algorithm to the permittivities determined here, the total concentration of impurities was determined to be about 9.8 times larger than the total concentration of the sample analyzed in [44]. In calculations, the temperature was set to 13 °C typical to *Unirea* mine and the frequency to 170 MHz.

This result could be interpreted in two ways. The first possible explanation is that the measurement site could be located in the peripheral areas of the diapir, where the mineral heterogeneity is usually high [53]. If this is the case, the salt deposit is much larger than it was initially believed. Let it be known that no actual measurements have ever been performed to estimate the total volume of the salt reservoir. There are only estimations of the volume closest to the surface, necessary for the industrial exploitation of the mine.

The second explanation is connected to the possibility that the rock salt has internally contained water in the pores’ interstices which make the rock salt a conductor for electric current. The water-induced conductivity in rock salt can be determined using the model in [54]. A common value of the conductivity induced by a 0.02% water content is $2 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$, estimated by a sampling procedure [24]. In terms of permittivity this produces an imaginary value of $\sim 10^{-2}$ for the considered bandwidth, which means that the high imaginary part obtained in Section III-A is not the result of impurities but of water trapped in the pores’ interstices. The structure of brine in grain boundaries of a halite has been under research over the past 30 years, and even though a number of innovative methods have been developed to study these structures, many details are still unclear and fundamental information is missing [56]. A full characterization of such structures is beyond the purpose of this article.

C. Statistical and Systematic Errors

The measurements in this article were performed in the main chamber of *Unirea* salt mine in Slanic Prahova (Romania), which provides a stable measurement environment between the measurement campaigns. Variations in results between campaigns are below 1% and may be attributed to the effect of an off-centered antenna when introduced in the boreholes [40]. This value was set as the statistical uncertainty.

As already mentioned in Section II-B, to eliminate the systematic errors introduced by the measurement setup a null calibration of the whole measuring system was performed (this also excludes reflection losses and changes in the measurement reference planes caused by the connection of most cables). The behavior of antennas can be described by the transfer function

H_{as} that is an intrinsic attribute of the antenna, defined independently on the distance between the transmitter and receiver (an eloquent description is provided in [40, Fig. 1]). The transfer function describes the antenna behavior in frequency, and it might incorporate other factors also (i.e., polarization and gain).

As presented in Section II-A, the only effect that cannot be modeled but is already included in the results on the behavior of the antennas' in salt is the scattering of radio waves on impurities within each layer. This systematically shows a mean standard deviation of $\sigma_H = 0.0082$ over the frequency band.

The parameters that describe the functionality of the antenna, namely $S_{12,as}$ and $S_{21,as}$, are directly proportional to the transfer function, and thus the uncertainty of H_{as} will propagate within the mathematical model and with the following fitting algorithm. To evaluate the overall model uncertainty introduced by the propagation of errors, the mean variance of the parameter Δ is to be determined, starting from (8) and (11) [57]

$$\sigma_{\Delta}^2 = \sum_p \sigma_{tot}^2 \left(\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial S_{11}} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

where σ_{tot}^2 represents the quadratic sum of systematic and statistical errors introduced by the scattering of impurities and off-centered antennas. This returns a value of $\sigma_{\Delta} = 0.0608$, which represents the overall contribution from unknown terms [mainly involved in (12)]. Due to the nonlinearity of (12), it was considered that this represents the upper value for the uncertainty of each parameter that appears in the model (e.g., permittivities and length of layers).

D. Implications for a Cosmic Neutrino Detector: Attenuation in the Medium

The first purpose of the work presented here is related to the possibility of building a cosmic radio neutrino detector in *Unirea* salt mine. For this the target material, i.e., salt, has to be carefully described and determined if the overall properties allow a cost efficient construction, feasible from the event-reconstruction point of view.

Since the focus is here on the medium, the effect of the instrumentation (mainly due to antennas) should be eliminated from the mathematical model. Equation (9)—compared to (2)—shows in a detailed manner how both the coupling of the instrumentation and the behavior of antennas in the dielectric medium affect the results. A proper description of the overall effect of the medium is given by

$$A = \frac{S_{21}}{(S_{12,as}S_{21,as})} = \frac{F_{12} \cdot F_{23} \cdot \dots \cdot F_{nm+1} A_{n+1}}{\Delta} \quad (16)$$

where S_{21} represents the measured transmission coefficient at a certain distance. Note that the Δ term still includes a contribution from the antenna, the term $S_{22,as}$. The presence of this term is decreasing the attenuation with a mean value of 2.16 dB in the considered frequency band.

The attenuation (expressed in decibels) is presented in Fig. 5. Some reference curves were introduced: the attenuation of radio waves in free space after 50 m of propagation,

Fig. 5. Attenuation in the salt mine after 10 m of propagation (green lines), 50 m of propagation (blue lines), and 100 m of propagation (red lines). The dash-dotted lines represent measured quantities. The continuous lines represent the attenuation of a lossy homogeneous medium with $\epsilon_r = 5.625 - j0.0708$. The dashed line shows the attenuation in free space after 50 m of propagation.

and the attenuation in a lossy homogeneous medium with a permittivity of $\epsilon_r = 5.625 - j0.0708$. The comparison with free space attenuation is presented as one of the main competitors for cosmic particle detectors in salt are the ones that use the atmosphere as target material.

For 100 m of propagation, the medium attenuates more the radio waves with ~ 25 dB compared to propagation in air at the same distance. The layered structure is responsible only for ~ 16 dB of the loss.

IV. CONCLUSION

Laboratory measurement of the complex permittivity of solid dielectrics at radio frequency has been the subject of many literature reports, but none of these approaches permits a 100-m scale detailed characterization of natural dielectrics, which represents the goal of this article.

The characteristics of the layers of sedimentary salt are determined from *in situ* measurements using an LMS fitting algorithm, based on a detailed propagation model for a heterogeneous medium, coupled with the antennas. The overall model uncertainty (that also includes propagation of errors resulted from the uncertainty of the boreholed antennas, $\sigma_H = 0.0082$ over the frequency band) was determined to be $\sigma_{\Delta} = 0.0608$. Due to the nonlinearity of equations it was considered that this represents the upper value for the uncertainty of each parameter that appears in the model (e.g. permittivities and length of layers).

Results show that the first 10 m of salt where the radio waves propagate are formed by 76 layers of salt, with thicknesses varying from 0.0045 to 0.278 m. The number of layers increases to 296 after 100 m of propagation (layers with a thickness of almost 1 m are also present). Regarding the validity of the model itself, it is worth mentioning that the previous work of the author reported a value of the permittivity of the first layer of salt to be $\epsilon_1 = 5.625 - j0.0708$ [40]. This is confirmed by laboratory work performed by Meng and

his collaborators [28] that found a value of $\Re\{\epsilon_r\} = 5.63 \pm 0.05$.

The method described in this article shows significant improvement compared to others reported in the literature: the work of Lambort et al. [38] retrieves thickness of only one layer of material, and one of air; 2-D electrical resistivity tomography allow media characterization with a resolution of 0.25–0.5 m and is also limited to highly irregular or complex geological features [47]; cross-hole GPR, generally requires that the boreholes where the emitters and receivers are inserted to be separated by 10 m at most [48], and in addition, they necessitate a high number of measurements, obtained with either a large number of receivers [49] or very long boreholes where the antennas are moved along [50].

Regarding the structure of *Unirea* mine it was also concluded that the high values of the imaginary part of the measured permittivity cannot be attributed to only sedimentary heterogeneity. Additional contribution must arise from the water trapped in the pores' interstices, or, one aspect that requires further investigation: the diapir is larger than it was initially believed (up to date there are no measurements on the total volume of the rock salt).

In the specific case of a radio cosmic neutrino detector in a salt ore, the cosmic particles are detected indirectly by measuring the radio waves produced at neutrinos' interaction with the salt, and thus attenuation introduced by radio wave propagation and the behavior of antennas in salt will essentially determine the construction limitations of the detector and also its reconstruction capabilities.

The overall results show that for 100 m of propagation in the salt rock, the medium attenuates the radio waves with about 80 dB in the frequency band 164–174 MHz. This value is with ~ 25 dB higher than the one obtained for propagation in air. The layered structure is responsible only for ~ 16 dB of the loss. These results are promising; however, the major concern of the author is connected to a large quantity of impurities or the water in the pores' interstices. This limits the reconstruction of the phase of the transfer function of antenna when positioned in a borehole in salt [40], and affects the reconstruction of events in terms of arrival direction.

APPENDIX CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SALT DIAPIR

The measurements in this article were performed in *Unirea* salt mine in Slanic Prahova (Romania), the largest salt mine complex in Europe, with a total surface of 80 000 m², whose exploitation started in 1943 [42]. *Unirea* salt mine is situated in a salt diapir formed in Early Miocene [31]. This salt dome represents a gigantic plug that has risen upward diapirically because of its low density into the overlying strata [31]. The original sedimentary salt deposits (situated at depths of several kilometers) started to flow upward under hydrostatic pressure through sediments of greater density, resulting in a domal structure of a lenticular shape [31].

Any salt reservoir could be subject to any of the four basic internal heterogeneous structures: domal heterogeneity, sedimentary heterogeneity, mineral heterogeneity, and structural heterogeneities [53].

The effects of the main domal heterogeneities are analyzed in Section III-B. As part of domal heterogeneity, other impurities are in forms of anhydrite (calcium sulfate) that forms a residual accumulation at the dome crest [53]. The effective-medium theory implies that the bulk dielectric constant is represented by a volume averaged mean dielectric constant of all constituents [18].

The effective medium theory, even though limited, was used as a first tool because in layered heterogeneous media the overall properties of the medium are effectively controlled by the root mean square average of the fluctuations in the local index of refraction over a volume element whose dimensions are of the order of the wavelength [18].

Trace amounts of quartz, feldspars, and carbonates in the form of SiO₂, NaAlSi₃O₈, and CaCO₃ (in concentrations of 0.5%–2% [31]), were added in the model. Theoretical variations in the imaginary part of permittivity were calculated and the variation was found to be less than 10% [58], and thus the low concentration of anhydrite specific to only peripheral area of diapirs will not influence the radio wave propagation discussed in this article.

Thick sedimentary beds are classified relatively as a homogeneous, nondispersive, isotropic, and linear medium. The inter-bedded layers are not a feature of salt diapirs due to the geological formation processes involved [53]. The sedimentary heterogeneity and its influence on radio wave propagation is discussed in Section II-A.

The multiminer development (i.e., the mineral heterogeneity) is of a complex nature and is usually located at the boundary of a sedimentary basin. The development of potassium salts in a majority of cases occurs like a frame around the rock salt body [53].

Structural heterogeneities of evaporate strata are generally the product of tectonic movements of the Earth's crust in the region of their deposition. It is specific to cap rocks or other types of folding structures [53] thus, together with the mineral heterogeneities, will not represent a case study here due to the depth of the mine chamber.

In the work addressed here porosities' effects were excluded as within the first 10 m of burial cementation reduces the porosity of halite crusts to less than 10% [59], [60]. The pore spaces in rock salt are almost completely filled at burial depths of 200 m [61], [62]. In addition, low levels of porosity do not influence the propagation of wavelength at meter orders (corresponding to the 170 MHz) [18].

Another geological property of a salt mine are the faulting structures. A problem associated with the step faults is that they can be a water feeder to the salt deposits.

Usually salt mines are natural water barriers as the upper impermeable layers (such as clay layers) protect the salt layers against water risk (infiltration or flooding) [63]. However, freshwater or slightly salted can cause the dissolution processes, forming salt karst. The dissolution process is very fast when cracks, faulting structures, joints, and bedding planes are present, forming pathways for water infiltration, that evolve into endokarst forms: sharp limestone pavements, sinkholes (collapse sinkholes, suffosions sinkholes) and enlarged cracks

on salt surfaces (generated by small sinkhole migration to the water infiltration place) [64].

The effect of brines in the form of fluid inclusions was already estimated in [32]. The brine-induced radio wave attenuation was calculated following [65], [66]. It is concluded that possible connate water and secondary trapped water [53] would absorb almost all radio electromagnetic radiation thus these forms of brine are unlikely to be present. This conclusion also applies for possible faulting structures that can be a water feeder to the salt deposits.

Such formations have been observed at different locations in the mine but not at the measurement site. Based on the lifetime of the mine and the long conservation allowed by the environment, it was concluded that water infiltration are not present at the site of the experiment. Implications of other forms of trapped water are discussed in Section III-B.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Romanian National Salt Company for the help provided with the operations in *Unirea* salt mine in Slanic Prahova, Romania.

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